

MINI DPR

(DETAILED PROJECT REPORT)

ABSTRACT

The Primary Use Of Travel Cup Is To Provide The Hot Water For Those Who Needed Especially For The Older People When Ever They Want. If We Are At Home, We Are Avail With Varieties Of Options Such As From The Fire Pit, Gas Stove, Induction Cooker As Well As The Electric Kettle Which Is The Way More Convenient And Simpler As Well As Easy To Use. But The Normal Electric Kettle Is Bulkier In Size And Not So Useful During The Journey. During A Journey, It Is Difficult To Keep A Hot Water With Us, So The Easiest Way Is To Produce The Hot Water Whenever We Need. So, We Are Having A Travel Cup Which Has The Dimensions Nearly To An Ordinary Cup Which Could Produce The Hot Water Within A Short Span Of Time, Convenient To Use, Cheaper, And Which Can Hold The Temperature For A Certain Period Of Time As Well As Which Could Operate Using Electricity. This DPR Will Discuss About The Technical Specifications As Well As Financial Aspects Of The Proposed Project Also The Feasibility Of The Proposed Idea.

INDEX

SI NO:	TITLE	PAGE NO:
1	INTRODUCTION	1
	1.1 OBJECTIVE	1
	1.2 BACKGROUND	1
	1.3 HIGH- LEVEL REQUIREMENT	2
2	BLOCK DIAGRAM	3
	2.1 BLOCK DISCRIPTIONS	3
	a. HEATING UNIT	3
	b. CONTROL UNIT	4
	c. SENSOR	4
	d. POWER SUPPLY	5
3	DESIGN SPECIFICATION	6
4	TECHNICAL SPECIFICATION	10
	4.1 FOR TRAIN SYSTEM	10
	4.2 FOR HOUSE HOLD SYSTEM	10
5	DEVICE SPECIFICATIONS	12
	5.1 VOLUME SPECIFICATIONS	12
6	MATERIAL SPECIFICATIONS	13
	6.1 GRAPHITE	13
	6.2 STEEL SECTIONS	13
	6.3 POLY URATHANE	14
	6.4 PLASTIC CASE	15
	6.5 HANDLE	16
	6.6 COASTER	16
	6.7 BASE	17
7	CIRCUITARY SPECIFICATIONS	18
	7.1 TEMPERATURE SENSOR	18
	7.2 PRESSURE SENSOR	19
	7.3 COOLING FAN	19
	7.4 IGBT	20
	7.5 ATmega 328p	20
		21

	7.7 CONNECTING WIRES	22
8	CODING	23
9	COST ESTIMATION	24
	9.1 RAW MATERIAL	24
	9.2 TRANSPORTATION	24
	9.3 INFRASTRUCTURE COST	25
	9.4 LABOUR COST	25
10	MARKET STUDY	27
	10.1 AGE GROUP (30-40)	27
	10.2 AGE GROUP (40-55)	27
	10.3 AGE GROUP (55-)	27
11	CONCLUSION	30
12	REFERENCES	31

1. INTRODUCTION

The Advent Of Travel Mugs Can Be Traced Back To The 1980s To Help People Who Were Travelling Preserve The Desired To Help People Who Were Travelling Preserve The Desired Temperatures Of Their Beverages. Whether One Wants Their Drink To Remain Cold Or Hot, A Travel Mug Helps Accomplish The Task Due To Thermal Insulation Properties. However, The Mug Is Not Sealed At All Times As The Drinking Opening At The Top Remains Open Leading To Heat Transfer With The Surrounding. The Temperature Of The Contained Beverage Is Greatly Affected By The Temperature Of Its Surroundings And Therefore, Hot Beverages Will Lose Their Optimum Desirable Temperature And That Applies For Cold Drinks As Well. Styrene And Plastic Cups Are Increasingly Being Utilized For The Purpose Of Carrying These Drinks As They Can Easily Be Warmed In A Microwave Without Destroying The Container. Consumers, Therefore, Tend To Focus On The Advantages Of Disposable Cups And Not Assume The Health Hazards That Can Be Caused By Styrene Cups And The Environmental Liability In Utilizing Plastic Cups. In Addition, The Reusable Mugs Are Not Able To Adequately Control The Temperature Of The Drink Contained In Them Over Extended Periods. The Heating And Cooling Processes Can Be Accomplished By Utilizing A Variety Of Methods Such As Resistive Heating And Refrigeration Cycles Respectively. In Addition, A Micro Thermoelectric Plate, A Peltier Element, Functions As A Heating And Cooling Source And Operates In Small Areas.

1.1 OBJECTIVE

Most Drinks Taste Differently At Different Temperatures, And It Is Certainly Nice To Enjoy Drinks At The Temperatures They Taste The Best[1]. However, Most Drinks Are Only Available At Their Storage Temperature, Which Is Either Room Or Refrigerator Temperature. There Are A Few Ways To Change The Temperature Of Drinks, Like Using A Microwave Or Refrigerator, But None Of These Methods Are Precise. Besides, Not Everyone Has Access To These Devices. For Example, A Dormitory Resident Probably Won't Buy A Refrigerator If Food Storage Is Not Needed, Even If It's Affordable. To Address The Inconvenience In Controlling The Temperature Of Drinks, We Plan To Develop An Electric Thermos Box. This Product Would Offer Users A Simple Way To Bring Any Drinks To Any Temperature They Want (Within Some Range, Of Course). Our Product Would Be Especially Beneficial To (1) People Like Dormitory Residents Who Do Not Have Access To Other Heating And Cooling Devices; And (2) People Who Want Precise Control Of The Temperatures Of Their Drinks.

1.2 BACKGROUND

Although Some Companies (Ember, Etc.) Have Been Developing A Temperature Controllable Mug, Most Of The Existing Thermos Cups Only Have Functions Of Heating The Liquid, And They Could Take As Long As An Hour To Get The Drinks Ready According To User

Reviews[2]. Also, There Is A Possible Problem With Burning Users' Hands Since The Heating Modules Are Usually Exposed To Air. The Device We Are Developing Would Not Only Be Able To Heat Up Drinks But Also To Cool Them Down. Furthermore, We Expect Our Device To Be Much More Efficient Than The Ones Currently On The Market.

1.3 HIGH-LEVEL REQUIREMENTS

- Our Product Should Be Able To Bring 250g Of Water To Any Desired Within The Range 0-100°C Starting From Room Temperature (20-30°C).
- The Entire Process Should Take No More Than 1.5 Minutes.
- The Final Temperature Should Have An Error Of At Most $\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$ Compared To The Desired Temperature.

1. BLOCK DIAGRAM

Figure 2.1

We Plan To Design A Cup Shaped Heater. To Heat The Drink, The User Must First Place The Cup Inside The Box, Then Plug The Device And Add The Water And Use Switches To Switch On The System. We Plan To Put All The Electronics On The Base Of The Cup And There Is A Coaster Accompanies With The Travel Cup Which Could Use As Well As Like A Coaster And A Lid Which Will Provide The Safety For The User.

2.1 BLOCK DESCRIPTIONS

2.1.1 HEATING UNIT

Power: Ac Input

Input: Control Signals From The Control Unit

Outputs: None

The Heating Unit Has Only One Mode Of Operation, Such That Once Water Is Added And Switched ON, The Coil Needed To Be Heated And Thus The Water Needed To Be Heated To The Temperature Of The Rate Of 100 Centigrade. Once It Reached 100 Centigrade The Heating Needed To Be Stopped So As To Protect The Cup As Well As To Eliminate The Power Wastage.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
1. Able to raise the temperature of 250 ml (250gm) of water from the room temperature (25-30 centigrade) to the 100 centigrade within 80 seconds under standard conditions.	I. Add 250 ml (250gm) of water or till the marked position of the cup II. Plug the instrument with cable provided. III. Place the coaster- lid on the top of the cup IV. Switch on the device by toggling the switch provided on the base of the travel cup V. Wait until the water gets its temperature and stops automatically

2.1.2 CONTROL UNIT

Power: 5V DC

Inputs: Temperature data, User requests, Safety Circuit

Outputs: Control signals to the heating

The Control Unit Will Take 3 Inputs. The Control Unit Will Control The Whole Operations Of The System. The Control Unit Will Work On The 5V DC Supply. The Control Unit Will Work Primarily On The Basis Of 3 Inputs. The Data From The Temperature Sensor, The Input From The Switch Which Is Determined By The User And The Input From The Safety Circuit.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
1. Needed To Switch On While The Switch Is In Closed Position. 2. Needed To Be Switched Off Once The Required Temperature Is Attained. 3. Only Needed To Be Switched Once The Lid Is Topped On The Top Of The Travel Cup	I. Check once the temperature of the water is rasing once the device is switched ON II. Check whether the device the turning off once the temperature (say 100 centigrade) is attained III. Check whether the device is turning ON without closing the lid-coaster

2.1.3 SENSORS

Input: 5V From the Power Supply

Outputs: Water Temperature Reading For The Control Unit, Pressure Reading From The Pressure Sensor To The Control Unit, LOGIC 0,1 From The Safety Network. This Module Measures The Temperature Of Water (Or Any Other Liquid Inside The Container), Measures The Pressure Developed As Well As Logic State From The Safety Network Provided And Sends The Measurement To The Control Unit. We Are Planning To Use A Contactless Sensor For This Module.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Should not be started until the Logic state is 1 2. There should be a resistance change once the temperature is changed 3. There should be some reading from the pressure sensor 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. Check whether there is a voltage once the lid is closed II. Check whether the resistance is changing once shown to flame III. Check whether there is a out once loaded

2.1.4 POWER SUPPLY

Outputs (Power): 5V For The Control Unit, Thermostat For Water, User Interface, Pressure Sensor And Temperature Sensor In Safety Module, Ac Supply From The Source To The Heating Element.

REQUIREMENT	VERIFICATION
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The voltage to the electronic part should be 5V 2. The supply to the heating element is the main supply itself. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> I. The out from the SMPS is of the order of 5V DC II. The supply to the heating coil is in the order of high voltage AC.

3. DESIGN SPECIFICATIONS

The Rough sketch will look like,

Figure 3.1

The cup consists of an heat sink for the electronic part which will control the entire device,

Figure 3.2

There Will Be A Coaster-Safety Lid For The Travel Cup So As To Ensure The Safety Of The Device For The User As Well As For The Device Itself. The Coaster-Safety Lid Is Designed In Such A Way That It Would Only Get Working Once The Coaster Is Used As Lid Correctly.

Figure 3.3

Figure 3.4

Figure 3.5

Figure 3.6

4. TECHNICAL SPECIFICATIONS

Amount of Energy needed to raise the temperature of water from room temperature to 100 centigrade,

$$Q = M * C * dT$$

M= mass of water, (say 250gm)

C= Specific Heat of Water, $4186 \approx 4200 \text{ j/kg}$

dT= (100-27) centigrade= 73 Centigrade

$$Q = 0.25 * 4200 * 73 = 76500 \text{ j} \approx 80000 \text{ j}$$

4.1 FOR TRAIN SYSTEM

Energy required = IVt

Where

I= current, (say 9A)

V= voltage, (110v)

Energy= 80kj

t= time, $E/(IV)$, $80 \text{ kj}/(110 * 9) = 81 \text{ s}$

Power= I^2R

I= current, (say 9A)

Power= Energy/time, $80 \text{ k}/81 = 987.654 \text{ W} \approx 990 \text{ W}$

R= W/I , $990/9 = 12.22 \Omega$

4.2 FOR HOUSE HOLD SYSTEM

Energy required = IVt

Where

I= current, (say 6A, For Normal Socket)

V= voltage, (240v)

Energy= 80kj

$$t = \text{time, } E/(IV), 80\text{kJ}/(240 * 9) = 56\text{s}$$

$$\text{Power} = I^2R$$

I = current, (say 9A)

$$\text{Power} = \text{Energy}/\text{time}, 80\text{k}/56 = 1428.57 \text{ W} \approx 1450 \text{ W}$$

$$R = W/I, 1450/6 = 241.66\Omega \approx 242 \Omega$$

So we Could use the heating coil with suitable material at appropriate dimensions.

Here we have chosen Spiral winding for the heating coil on the bottom of the travel cup which will heats up the water to the required temperature.

As we know, $R = (\rho l)/A$

$$l = \text{length } (2*\pi*r), (2*\pi*3.95) = 0.2482 \text{ M}$$

$$A = \text{Area of Cross-section } (\pi*r*r), (\pi*1*1*10^{-6}) = 3.14*10^{-6} \text{ M}^2$$

$$\rho = \text{Resistivity, } RA/l, (12.5*3.14*10^{-6})/0.2482 = 1.58*10^{-4} \Omega\text{M}$$

5. DEVICE SPECIFICATIONS

5.1 VOLUME SPECIFICATIONS

- Optimised Along With as many calculations.
- We are supposed to design a travel cup of volume 250 ML, for that we need to design a travel cup of having capacity of 300 ML
- We are fixing height of the top of the cup at 10CM.

$$0.1 \times \pi \int_{3.95}^6 r \times dr = 0.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}^3 \text{ of volume.}$$

- The travel cup is supposed to design in a tapered shape just like normal cup we uses daily.
- So the specifications of the travel cup are
 - Base radiu s= 3.95 CM
 - Top Radius = 6 CM
 - Hieght = 10 CM
 - Bottom area, $\pi r^2 = \pi \times 3.95^2 = 4.9 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}^2$
 - Top Area, $\pi r^2 = \pi \times 6^2 = 11.3 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}^2$
 - Bottom Perimeter, $2 \times \pi \times r = 2 \times \pi \times 3.95 = 0.248 \text{ M}$
 - Top perimeter, $2 \times \pi \times R = 2 \times \pi \times 6 = 0.377 \text{ M}$

6. MATERIAL SPECIFICATIONS

6.1 GRAPHITE

$$\text{Volume} = \pi r^2 l$$

r = radius, (1MM)

l = length (0.248M)

$$\text{Volume} = \pi * 10^{-6} * 0.248 = 7.79 * 10^{-7}$$

Density of Graphite = 2260 Kg/M³

$$\text{Mass} = \text{Density} * \text{volume}, 2260 * 7.79 * 10^{-7} = 1.76 \text{gm} \approx 2 \text{gm}$$

6.2 STEEL SECTION

Figure 6.1

$$D = 6 \times 10^{-2} \text{M}$$

$$D = 3.95 \times 10^{-2} \text{M}$$

$$H = 0.1 \text{M}$$

$$P = \pi \times D, \pi \times 6 \times 10^{-2} = 0.188 \text{M}$$

$$P' = \pi \times d, \pi \times 3.95 \times 10^{-2} = 0.124 \text{M}$$

$$\text{Thickness} = 0.188 - 0.124 = 0.064 \text{M}$$

$$A = 0.124 \times 0.1 = 0.0124 \text{M}^2$$

$$A' = 0.064 \times 0.1 = 6.4 \times 10^{-3} \text{M}^2$$

$$A_{\text{Total}} = A + A', 0.0124 + 0.0064 = 0.0188 \text{M}^2$$

Volume= Area x Thickness

Thickness= 1MM

$$V = 0.0188 \times 1 \times 10^{-3}$$

VOLUME OF BASE:

$$V' = \frac{\pi}{4} \times d^2 \times t, \frac{\pi}{4} \times (3.95 \times 10^{-2})^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-3} = 2.45 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}^3$$

$$V_{\text{Total}} = 2.125 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}^3$$

$$\text{Mass} = V \times \text{density}, 2.125 \times 10^{-5} \times 7850 = 0.16681 \text{ Kg}$$

$$166.81 \text{ gm} \approx 170 \text{ gm}$$

6.3 POLY URETHANES

Figure 6.2

$$A_{\text{Total}} = A + A', 0.124 \times 10^{-4} + 2 \times 0.5 \times 1.5 \times 10^{-4} = 1.624 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}^2$$

$$\text{Volume} = \text{Area} \times \text{Thickness}, 1.624 \times 10^{-4} \times 1.5 \times 10^{-3} = 2.436 \times 10^{-7}$$

$$\text{Density} = 6 \text{-Kg/M}^3$$

$$\text{Mass} = \text{Volume} \times \text{Density}, 60 \times 2.436 \times 10^{-7} = 1.4616 \times 10^{-5} \text{ Kg}$$

6.4 PLASTIC CASE

Figure 6.3

Diameter, $D = 0.065\text{M}$

$$P_1 = \pi \times D, \pi \times 0.065 = 0.204\text{M}$$

$$P_2 = \pi \times d, \pi \times 0.0445 = 0.140\text{M}$$

$H = 0.1\text{M}$

$$d = 44.5\text{MM} = 0.0445\text{ M}$$

$$A_1 = 0.140 \times 0.1 = 0.0140\text{ M}^2$$

$$A_2 = 0.064 \times 0.1 = 0.0064\text{ M}^2$$

$$P_1 - P_2 = 0.064\text{ M}$$

$$A_{\text{Total}} = 0.014 + 0.0064 = 0.0204\text{ M}^2$$

$$\text{Volume} = \text{Area} \times \text{Thickness}, 0.0204 \times 1.5 \times 10^{-3} = 3.06 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M}^3$$

$$V' = \frac{\pi}{4} \times d^2 \times t, \frac{\pi}{4} \times 0.0445^2 \times 1.5 \times 10^{-3} = 2.33 \times 10^{-6}$$

$$V_{\text{Total}} = V + V' = 3.06 \times 10^{-5} + 2.33 \times 10^{-6} = 3.293 \times 10^{-5}\text{ M}^3$$

$$\text{Density} = 650\text{Kg/M}^3$$

$$\text{Mass} = \text{density} \times \text{Volume}, 3.292 \times 10^{-5} \times 650 = 0.0214\text{ Kg}$$

6.5 HANDLE

Figure 6.4

Total Volume of Handle, $3.2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}^3$

Mass= Volume x Density, $3.2 \times 10^{-6} \times 970 = 3.104 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Kg}$

6.6 COASTER

Figure 6.5

6.7 BASE

Let radius R_1 varies from 3.95 to 3.5 CM

$$\text{Area} = \int_{3.5}^{3.95} 2 \times \pi \times R \times dR = 2\pi [R^2/2]_{3.5}^{3.95} = 2\pi \times 1.676 = 10.53 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$$

Thickness = 1.5 MM

$$\text{Volume} = At = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \times 10.53 \times 10^{-4} = 1.5795 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}^3$$

$$\text{Mass} = \text{Volume} \times \text{density}, 1.5795 \times 10^{-6} \times 970 = 1.532 \times 10^{-3} \text{ Kg}$$

Total weight without the Circuitry and control systems is

$$1.6 + 170 + 1.76 + 0.6 + 22 + 3.1 + 6.65 = 205.71 \text{ gm}$$

7. CIRCUITARY SPECIFICATIONS

Here In This Work We Are Using 2 Sensors Along With A Safety System Which Will Made Avail Along With The Coaster. The System Will Be Turned On If And Only If All The 3 Conditions Satisfies. We Are Also Using An SMPS To Convert The Main AC Into 5V DC So That It Could Be Used In Electronic Circuits.

7.1 TEMPERATURE SENSOR

The Proposed Device Consists Of Six Main Parts: Microcontroller, Heater Driver Circuit, Temperature Sensor, Temperature Display, Reference Temperature Input And Control Algorithm. Microcontroller Acts As Main Brain For The Device. It Provides Automated Control Of Temperature Reading, Microcontroller Atmega 328p Is Chosen This Project Since It Provides Large Library And Wide Hardware Support. To Enable To Capability Of Temperature Control Inside Kettle, Temperature Sensor Should Be Utilized. DS18B20 Temperature Sensor Is Used Since It Is Water-Proof And Compatible To Be Interfaced To Any Microcontroller Using A Single Digital Pin, And Even Possible To Connect Multiple Same Sensors To The Same Pin. The Sensor Has A Unique 64-Bit ID Burned-In At The Factory To Differentiate Them Which Enable The Multiple Connection At The Same Pin Of Microcontroller. Power Supply For The Sensor Is 3.0-5V And Capable To Measure Temperature Range From -55°C To 125°C . For Heater Driver Circuit, Solid State Relay SSR Is Used Since It Is Easy To Be Interfaced Between Microcontroller And AC Power Supply. It Is Constructed Based On TRIAC-Based Circuit. It Should Be Noted That To Drive SSR To Control AC Voltage, Low Frequency PWM (E.G: 0.1 Times Than The AC Voltage Frequency) Should Be Used To Obtain Uniform Cycle Of AC Voltage. High Frequency PWM (E.G. PWM Frequency Less Frequency Of AV Voltage) Of Driving SSR Will Induce Non-Uniform Phase Angle Of AC Voltages Thus Making Linear Relationship Between Heater Power And PWM Duty Cycle Is Not Possible. In This Work, Low Frequency PWM Can Be Used For Water Temperature Control Since Water Temperature Has Slow Step Response.

Image shown is a representation only. Exact specifications should be obtained from the product data sheet.

Figure 7.1

7.2 PRESSURE SENSOR

The BMP180 Is The Function Compatible Successor Of The BMP08 A New Generation Of High Precision Digital Pressure Sensors For Consumer Applications. The Ultra Low Power, Low Voltage Electronics Of The BMP180 Is Optimized For Use In Mobile Phones, Pdas, GPS Navigation Devices And Outdoor Equipment. With A Low Altitude Noise Of Merely 0.25m At Fast Conversion Time, The BMP180 Offers Superior Performance. The IC Interface Allows For Easy System Integration With A Micro Controller. The BMP180 Is Based On Piezo Resistive Technology For EMC Robustness, High Accuracy And Linearity As Well As Long Term Stability. Robert Bosch Is The World Market Leader For Pressure Sensors In Automotive Applications. Based On The Experience Of Over Million Pressure Sensors In The Field, The BMP180 Continues A New Generation Of Micro Machined Pressure Sensors.

Parameter	Symbol	Condition	Min	Typ	Max	Units
Operating temperature	T_A	operational	-40		+85	°C
		full accuracy	0		+65	
Supply voltage	V_{DD}	ripple max. 50mVpp	1.8	2.5	3.6	V
			1.62	2.5	3.6	
Supply current @ 1 sample / sec. 25°C	I_{DDLOW}	ultra low power mode		3		µA
	I_{DDSTD}	standard mode		5		µA
	I_{DDHR}	high resolution mode		7		µA
	I_{DDUHR}	Ultra high res. mode		12		µA
	I_{DDAR}	Advanced res. mode		32		µA
Peak current	I_{PEAK}	during conversion		650		µA
Standby current	I_{DDSBM}	@ 25°C		0.1	4 ¹	µA
Relative accuracy pressure $V_{DD} = 3.3V$		950 ... 1050 hPa @ 25 °C		±0.12		hPa
		700 ... 900hPa 25 ... 40 °C		±1.0		m
Absolute accuracy pressure $V_{DD} = 3.3V$		300 ... 1100 hPa 0 ... +65 °C	-4.0	-1.0*	+2.0	hPa
		300 ... 1100 hPa -20 ... 0 °C	-6.0	-1.0*	+4.5	hPa
Resolution of output data		pressure		0.01		hPa
		temperature		0.1		°C
Noise in pressure		see table on page 12-13				
Absolute accuracy temperature $V_{DD} = 3.3V$		@ 25 °C	-1.5	±0.5	+1.5	°C
		0 ... +65 °C	-2.0	±1.0	+2.0	°C

¹ at 85°C

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 Note: Specifications within this document are subject to change without notice.

Figure 7.2

7.3 COOLING FAN

Once The System Works, The Coil Will Generate The Heat Which Will Damage The Microcontroller Placed In Bottom, So We Are Using An Cooling Fan For Cooling The Microcontroller So As To Ensure The Longevity Of The Microcontroller. The Specifications Are Given Below.

Operating Voltage: 5V
Current: 0.2 A
Brushless DC Fan
Fan Dimensions: 30mm X 30mm X 8mm
Wire Length: 3.25" / 80mm
Fan Weight: 6.2g

Figure 7.3

7.4 IGBT

The IRG4BC30UD Is An Insulated Gate Bipolar Transistor With Ultrafast Soft Recovery Diode. Its Is Designed To Be A "Drop-In" Replacement For Equivalent Industry-Standard Generation 3 IR Igbts. It Is Optimized For Specific Application Conditions. The Generation 4 Igbts Offers The Highest Efficiencies Available. The HEXFRED Diodes Optimized For Performance With Igbts And The Minimized Recovery Characteristics Require Less/No Snubbing.

Figure 7.4

	Parameter	Max.	Units
V _{CES}	Collector-to-Emitter Voltage	600	V
I _C @ T _C = 25°C	Continuous Collector Current	23	A
I _C @ T _C = 100°C	Continuous Collector Current	12	
I _{CM}	Pulsed Collector Current ①	92	
I _{LM}	Clamped Inductive Load Current ②	92	
I _F @ T _C = 100°C	Diode Continuous Forward Current	12	
I _{FM}	Diode Maximum Forward Current	92	
V _{GE}	Gate-to-Emitter Voltage	± 20	V
P _D @ T _C = 25°C	Maximum Power Dissipation	100	W
P _D @ T _C = 100°C	Maximum Power Dissipation	42	
T _J	Operating Junction and	-55 to +150	°C
T _{STG}	Storage Temperature Range		
	Soldering Temperature, for 10 sec.	300 (0.063 in. (1.6mm) from case)	
	Mounting Torque, 6-32 or M3 Screw.	10 lbf·in (1.1 N·m)	

Thermal Resistance

Parameter	Min.	Typ.	Max.	Units
R _{θJC}	-----	-----	1.2	°C/W
R _{θJC}	-----	-----	2.5	
R _{θCS}	-----	0.50	-----	
R _{θJA}	-----	-----	80	
Wt	-----	2 (0.07)	-----	g (oz)

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Figure 7.5

7.5 ATmega 328p

The Atmega328 Is A Single-Chip Microcontroller Created By Atmel In The Megaavr Family (Later Microchip Technology Acquired Atmel In 2016). It Has A Modified Harvard Architecture 8-Bit RISC Processor Core. The Atmel 8-Bit AVR RISC-Based Microcontroller Combines 32 KB ISP Flash Memory With Read-While-Write Capabilities, 1 KB EEPROM, 2 KB SRAM, 23 General-Purpose I/O Lines, 32 General-Purpose Working Registers, 3 Flexible Timer/Counters With Compare Modes, Internal And External Interrupts, Serial Programmable USART, A Byte-Oriented 2-Wire Serial Interface, SPI Serial Port, 6-Channel 10-Bit A/D Converter (8 Channels In TQFP And QFN/MLF Packages), Programmable Watchdog Timer With Internal Oscillator, And 5 Software-Selectable Power-Saving Modes. The Device Operates Between 1.8 And 5.5 Volts. The Device Achieves Throughput Approaching 1 MIPS/Mhz.

Parameter	Value
CPU type	8-bit AVR
Maximum CPU speed	20 MHz
Performance	20 MIPS at 20 MHz ^[2]
Flash memory	32 KB
SRAM	2 KB
EEPROM	1 KB
Package pin count	28 or 32
Capacitive touch sensing channels	16
Maximum I/O pins	23
External interrupts	2
USB interface	No

Figure 7.5

Figure 7.6

7.6 CONNECTING CABLE

We Are Using The 1.5 MM² Standard Gauge Wire So That It Could Carry 9A Of Current Without Any Trouble For Longer Term Usage Even Though The Standard 1 MM² Is Capable Of Carrying 11A, But When We Consider About The Long Term Usage, We Could Go For 1.5 MM². The Spec Sheet And Details Of The Chord And The Wire Is Given Below. We Are Planning To Give 80 CM Of Chord Length And The Chord Is Directly From Mains To TYPE C So That Some One Could Use It Very Convenient Way And Which Is More Universally Accepted. The Fuse Is Type Of Cartridge Which Will Ensure The Safety Of The Entire System. The Reason Behind The Selection Of Cartridge Type Fuse, It Is Very Compact And It Could Easily Replaceable And Cheap so that it could easily replaced by the user it self once it is finished its life time. The terminals of the Plug is of the size of 6 MM made of stainless steel. The fuse is of the dimension of 5MM x 20MM.

Figure 7.7

We Use Normal Plus Of Indian Standard As We Are Planning To Implement The Product In To The Indian Market As Of Now And The Market Study Is Based On The Indian Economy. We need to give the connecting wires as well as the circuit board so as to connect the electronic components to integrate all the components so as increase the efficiency as well as compactness of the equipment.

8. CODING

The flowchart of the entire system is given below in which all the operations of the system is working conditionally.

Figure 8.1

9. COST ESTIMATION

9.1 RAW MATERIAL

SI NO:	MATERIAL	PRICE/UNIT	REQUIRED QUANTITY	AMOUNT
1	FLEXIBLE GRAPHITE	550/KG	2 gm	1.5
2	STAINLESS STEEL	150/KG	170 gm	29
3	POLYUTHANE	200/KG	1.4616 x 10 ⁻⁵ Kg	0.1
4	PLASTIC	80/KG	32.686 gm	3
5	TEMPERATURE SENSOR	54/PSC	1	54
6	PRESSURE SESNOR	40/PSC	1	40
7	IGBT	65/PSC	1	65
8	ATMEGA 328 P	70/PSC	1	70
9	PLUG	32/PSC	1	32
10	USB TYPE C	4.5, 10/PSC	1,1	14.5

9.2 TRANSPORTATION

The Manufacturing Plant Is Supposed To Build In Kanji Kode Near Palakkad Which Is Very Favorable For Different Kind Of Industry Where The Land Cost Is Also Cheap And The All Basic Requirement To Start The Industry Is There. Kanji Kode Is Also Very Accessible With Different Kind Of Transportation Such As Road, Rail And Kanji Kode Is Nearer To Coimbatore So That It Could Also Easily Accessible Through Air. The Amount For The Transportation Of The Manufactured Units Is Given Below. The Districts Are Classified As Groups So That The Transportation Of Manufactured Units Over The Roads Can Be Done In A Optimistic Way So That We Could Cut Down The Cost To An Extend Which Will Increase The Profit Margin By Cutting Down Un-Necessary Expenses.

SI NO:	DISTRICTS	DISTANCE	AMOUNT
1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • TRIVANDRUM • KOLLAM • ALAPPUZHA • PATHANAMTHITTA • KOTTAYAM 	342	1500
2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • THRISSUR • COCHIN 	148	700
3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MALAPPURAM • KOZHIKODE • WAYANAD 	191	850
4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KANNUR • KASARGOD 	314	1400

We Had Created The Table By Assuming We Are Having A Midrange Low End Vehicle So As To Transport The Manufactured Products Across The Kerala. The Assumed Vehicle Is Of Having A Milage Of 22 Km/ L.

9.3 INFRASTRUCTURE COST

As We Are Starting In This Field With No Other Business, We Are Planning To Implement Something Small But Not Too Small. We Are Having To Lease The Land For The Construction Of Required Buildings And All Other Parameters.

As Of Now, We Are Having The Details Given Below.

Land	55000/Month
Infrastructure	2000000
Plant & Machinery	1000000
Vehicles	1000000
Office Automation	150000
Preliminary Operation	250000
Working Capital	1000000
Marketing	400000

9.4 LABOUR COST

POST	REQUIRED NO:	PAYMENT	TOTAL
General Manager	1	200000	200000
Technical Operator	2	450000	900000
Engineer	2	1000000	2000000
Diploma Engineer	6	500000	3000000
Supervisor	1	450000	450000
Accountant	2	250000	500000
Medical Officer	1	700000	700000
Cleaning Staff	3	150000	450000
Security	2	200000	400000

So, We Could Implement Our Proposed Projects Within A Stipulated Capital Money Of 70 Lakhs. We Could Cut Down The Expenses As We Optimize All These Constraints.

The Expense For Us To Make A Single Piece Of Travel Cup Is Around 300, We Could Sell This Product For Rupees 450 Which Includes The 50 Rupees Commission Of The Shop Keeper Or The Sales Man/Women.

As We Sale For This Amount, At A Rate 1000 Pieces A Month All Over The Kerala, We Could Sell 12000 Units A Year, So That We Could Make A Profit Of 120000 A Year So That We Could Take Our Investments Back Within A Period Of 7 Years.

10. MARKET STUDY

The Ultimate Aim Behind Every Innovation Is To Make People Life More Easier. In Now On Days In The World Of Technology, Every Think Is Changing Very Quick And Rapid. Every Product Which Is Coming To The Market Needed To Be Clutched In The Market. For That We Need A Fully Packed Market Study. The Travel Cup Is Very Well Useful For The Age Group Of Kids Like 1-4 And For The Elder People Of Age 45-80. For The Age Group Of 1-4, The Product Market Need To Be Focused Among The Customers Having Age Of 29-40. So To Be Short, We Need To Market The Product Among The Customers Of Age Group Between 30-80. We Could Classify The Age Group Into 3 Such As 30-40, 40-55, 55-80 And Lets Break It Down For More Details.

10.1 AGE GROUP (30-40)

These Age Groups Are Backbone For The Future Society. They Are Most Young And Dynamic Customers We Could Ever Met. These Age Group Customers Will Tends To Spend More As They Are Not Very Well Planned And They Are Getting The Rhythm Of The Life And They Are Not Very Well Detailed About The Future As They Are Adventurous. They Are More Likely To Buy A Product Without Having A Second Thought In Most Time. As They Are The Younger Generation Who Witnessed The Sudden Growth Of Technology, They Are Very Well Bonded With The Smart Technology, So We Need To Reach Them Through Electronic Media Such As Social Media Like Instagram, Snapchat, Facebook Etc. For That We Need Kickass Videos And Posters As Well As We Need A Good Digital Marketing Team Whose Know Very Well About Digital Marketing As Well As Search Engine Optimization.

10.2 AGE GROUP (40-55)

These Age Group Are Middle Agers Who Are Not Dynamic As Well. In The Life Time Of Human. For The Current Scenario, By The Life Style We Have Now, Everybody Are Getting Diabetic And Having All Other Lifestyle Deceases. So They Are Getting More Conscious As Well As They Are Very Well Bothered About Their Future As Their Children Are Getting Growing And They Will Starts Investing Heavily On The Stocks, Mutual Funds And They Will Think Twice Before They Do Every Think. So This Age Group Customers Are Not Dynamic And They Will Not Buy Our Product And Services Just Like Younger Customers. They Will Feel Like They Are Getting Exhausted And Much More And There Will Be Some Changes In Their Life Style Too.

10.3 AGE GROUP (55-)

These Age Group Are Most Likely Retired Ones Or Tends To Retire, They Spend Rest Of Their Life Without Having Much Worries Or Tension As Their Children Are Getting Self-Sustain And They Are Having Their Own Income And Much More. From The Age Of 60 Most

Of The People Will Withdraw To Them Selves As The Lifestyle Deceases Are Having Much More Bigger Clutches On Them Which Is Not Good For Them They Are Likely To Have Money To Spend On The Medicals An As Well As Devices Just Like This Which Are More Way Convenient For Them To Use. These Age Group People Will Also Spend More On The Devices Like Travel Cup As They Tends To Travel More And Product Like Ours To Make Their Life Hassle Free.

Our Product Have A World Wide Market As The Travel Cup Is Used By Every Traveler Across The Globe And It Has No Restrictions. For The Time Being We Could Have A Market Study Of Travel Cup On India. As the life style of customers in India is changing a lot, the younger generation are willing to take more adventurous, and they are most likely to travel within the India as well as to outside India. The plot shown below will state the proof.

Year	No. of Indian Nationals' departures from India	Percentage change over the previous year
2013	16626316	11.4
2014	18332319	10.3
2015	20376307	11.1
2016	21871995	7.3
2017	23942957	9.5
2018	26296484	9.8

Source: Bureau of Immigration, India

Figure 10.1

The Port-Wise Number Of Indian National's Departures From India For 2011 To 2018, Are Given In During 2018, Top 3 Airports For Departures Of Indian Nationals From India Were Delhi, Mumbai, And Chennai. Delhi Airport Registered The Highest Share (22.06%) Followed By Mumbai Airport (20.75%) And Chennai Airport (8.98%). These 3 Top Airports Accounted For 51.79% Of The Total Departures In 2018. During 2017, Delhi, Mumbai, And Cochin Airports Had A Percentage Share Of 21.38%, 21.29% And 9.25%, Respectively. The Share Of Top 10 Ports In Overall Departures Of Indian Nationals From India During 2011-2018 Has Also Gradually Decreased From 91.38% In 2011 To 87.87% In 2018. This Decline May Be Due To Various Reasons Including Introduction Of International Flights At Other Airports.

The common middle class of India will depend upon the Indian Railway services and their statistics is given below.

Figure 10.2

We Are Unavailable With The Data From Road Travelling. Many Of The People Around Us Are Having Their Trip Through Road System Which Is Almost Impossible To Figure Out That How Many Passengers Are Travelled Through This System. To Be Short, The Mentality Of The People In Now On Days Are Getting Changed Which Is Very Beneficial For Our Business.

The average consumption of Tea in India is plotted Below which will tell us that, our product is having an open market in India As making tea is one of the applications of our proposed project.

Figure 10.3

As the graph is increasing which indicates the increasing tea consumption in India, which ensures the future scope of the proposed project.

11.CONCLUSION

As Of This Is The Mini DPR Which Will Give Us A Basic Outline Of The Proposed Project, We Could Implement The Proposed Project With This Document. The Travel Cup Is One Of The Most Used Concept In The Day To Day Life Of An Indian Citizen As, Most Of The Indian Citizens Are Using The Hot Water For Drinking As Well Most On Indian Are Drinking The Chai More Than Any Other Drink. So There Is A Huge Market For This Travel Cup And If We Implement This, We Could Raise The More Profit And We Could Solve A Common Man's Day To Day Problem.

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